

TO EVALUATE THE FREQUENCY OF INFECTION IN FEMALES INDUCED WITH INTRACERVICAL FOLEY'S AFTER PROM (>37 WEEKS) COMPARED TO THOSE WITH EXPECTANT MANAGEMENT

Mubashra Khan^{*1}, Nighat Ali Shah², Zarmina Khan Mandokhail³, Dr. Israr Khan Roshan⁴

¹Postgraduate Trainee, Gynaecology and Obstetrics, MBBS, JPMC Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

²HOD Gynaecology and Obstetrics, FCPS, JPMC Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

³Visiting Lecturer, MPhil in Physiology and Endocrinology, University of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan

⁴Registrar Psychiatry, MCPS, Beaumont Hospital, Dublin, Ireland

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Corresponding Author: *

Mubashra Khan

Abstract

Background:

Prelabour rupture of membranes (PROM) at term is a common obstetric condition associated with an increased risk of maternal and neonatal infections, particularly when there is a delay between membrane rupture and delivery. Induction of labour is often recommended to reduce infectious morbidity; however, the choice of induction method remains controversial. Mechanical methods such as the intracervical Foley catheter have gained attention due to their safety, cost-effectiveness, and lower risk of uterine hyper stimulation.

Objective:

To compare the frequency of maternal infections in females with PROM at term (≥ 37 weeks) induced with an intracervical Foley catheter versus those managed expectantly.

Methodology:

This case-control study will be conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi over a period of six months. A total of 200 pregnant females with PROM at term will be enrolled using a simple random sampling technique. Participants will be divided into two groups: one group undergoing labour induction intracervical Foley catheter and the other managed expectantly. Baseline investigations including total leukocyte count (TLC), C-reactive protein (CRP), urine detailed report, and high vaginal swab will be performed. Participants will be monitored for signs of infection during labour and followed for up to two weeks postpartum. Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 21, and outcomes will be compared between both groups.

Results:

It is anticipated that induction of labour intracervical Foley catheter will not significantly increase the risk of maternal infection compared to expectant management and may reduce the duration between PROM and delivery.

Conclusion:

Intracervical Foley catheter is expected to be a safe and effective method for labour induction in PROM at term, particularly in low-resource settings, with no significant increase in maternal infectious morbidity.

INTRODUCTION

Prelabour rupture of membranes (PROM) is defined as the rupture of fetal membranes before the onset of labour after 37 completed weeks of gestation (Caughey et al., 2008). It is a common obstetric condition, occurring in approximately 8% of term pregnancies, and is associated with significant maternal and neonatal risks, particularly infection (Hannah et al., 1996). The duration between membrane rupture and delivery is a critical determinant of outcomes, as prolonged intervals increase the likelihood of ascending infections such as chorioamnionitis and neonatal sepsis (Nakubulwa et al., 2015; Tita & Andrews, 2010).

The pathophysiology of PROM is multifactorial, involving complex biochemical, mechanical, and infectious processes. Intrauterine infections and inflammatory responses contribute significantly to the weakening of fetal membranes, leading to rupture (French & McGregor, 1996). Women with underlying genital tract infections are particularly vulnerable due to the release of inflammatory mediators that compromise membrane integrity (Nakubulwa et al., 2015). These mechanisms place both the mother and neonate at increased risk of morbidity.

The management of PROM at term remains controversial, with two primary approaches: expectant management and active management through induction of labour. Expectant management allows spontaneous onset of labour but may increase the risk of infection due to prolonged membrane rupture. Conversely, induction of labour aims to reduce infectious morbidity by shortening the interval between PROM and delivery (Delorme et al., 2021). However, the optimal method of induction continues to be debated.

Successful induction of labour depends largely on effective cervical ripening. Mechanical methods, particularly the intracervical Foley catheter, have gained widespread acceptance due to their safety and efficacy (Niromanesh et al., 2003; Greenberg & Khalifeh, 2015). The Foley catheter facilitates cervical ripening through direct mechanical dilation and stimulation of endogenous prostaglandin release (Lee et al., 2020). Compared

to pharmacological agents, it is associated with a lower risk of uterine hyperstimulation and is considered a safer option in certain high-risk obstetric conditions (Haavisto et al., 2021).

Recent studies have explored the use of mechanical methods in PROM and suggest that intracervical Foley catheter is a safe and effective option for labour induction, particularly when used with appropriate infection control measures (Kruit et al., 2020; Hayat, 2021). However, concerns regarding the risk of ascending infection remain, especially in cases where the natural protective barrier has already been compromised. Despite growing global evidence, there is a lack of local data evaluating the safety and effectiveness of intracervical Foley catheter use in PROM in Pakistan. Given the need for cost-effective and safe interventions in low-resource settings, further research is essential.

Therefore, this study aims to compare the frequency of maternal infections in females with PROM at term who are induced using an intracervical Foley catheter versus those managed expectantly. The findings will contribute to evidence-based clinical practice and may help optimize management strategies for PROM in similar healthcare settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Prelabour rupture of membranes (PROM) at term remains a significant obstetric concern due to its association with maternal and neonatal infections. The management of PROM, particularly the choice between expectant management and active induction of labour, has been widely studied, with varying conclusions regarding safety and effectiveness.

Several studies support active management of PROM through induction of labour to reduce infectious morbidity. A landmark randomized controlled trial by Hannah et al. (1996) demonstrated that induction of labour using oxytocin was associated with a lower risk of maternal infection compared to expectant management, without increasing cesarean section rates. Similarly, Shah and Doshi (2012) reported that early induction significantly reduced maternal and neonatal morbidity, shortened hospital stay,

and did not increase operative delivery rates, supporting induction as a preferred management strategy.

Mechanical methods of induction, particularly the intracervical Foley catheter, have gained increasing attention due to their safety profile. Niromanesh et al. (2003) and Greenberg and Khalifeh (2015) highlighted that Foley catheter is an effective method for cervical ripening with minimal risk of uterine hyperstimulation. Furthermore, Lee et al. (2020) demonstrated that combining intracervical Foley catheter with pharmacological agents such as misoprostol enhances the efficiency of labour induction without significantly increasing complications.

Recent studies have specifically evaluated the safety of Foley catheter use in PROM cases. Krut et al. (2020) conducted a cohort study and concluded that balloon catheter is a safe method for cervical ripening in women with PROM when appropriate prophylactic antibiotics are used, with no significant increase in maternal or neonatal infections. Similarly, Hayat (2021) found that the use of intracervical Foley catheter, either alone or in combination with misoprostol, reduces the induction-to-delivery interval without increasing the risk of chorioamnionitis.

In contrast, some studies suggest that combining mechanical and pharmacological methods may not always provide additional benefits. Amorosa et al. (2017) reported no significant difference in delivery time when comparing concurrent Foley catheter and oxytocin use with oxytocin alone in nulliparous women with PROM. This highlights the need for careful selection of induction methods based on individual patient characteristics.

Infectious morbidity remains a central concern in PROM management. Tita and Andrews (2010) emphasized that prolonged rupture of membranes significantly increases the risk of chorioamnionitis, which can lead to severe maternal and neonatal complications. The role of antibiotic prophylaxis has also been explored, with Melis et al. (2007) demonstrating that timely antibiotic therapy can reduce intra-amniotic infection and prolong pregnancy in selected cases.

More recent evidence suggests that individualized management approaches may be beneficial. D'Ambrosi et al. (2022) reported that immediate induction in high-risk patients with PROM resulted in outcomes comparable to expectant management in low-risk patients, suggesting that universal induction may not always be necessary. Similarly, Devillard et al. (2019) found that mechanical methods, particularly balloon catheters combined with oxytocin, can shorten the induction-to-delivery interval effectively.

Despite the growing body of international evidence, there remains a lack of region-specific data, particularly in low-resource settings such as Pakistan. Most studies have been conducted in high-income countries where access to healthcare resources and infection control measures may differ significantly.

Therefore, there is a need for locally conducted studies to evaluate the safety, effectiveness, and cost-efficiency of intracervical Foley catheter use in PROM. This study aims to address this gap by comparing infection rates between intracervical Foley catheter induction and expectant management in a tertiary care hospital setting in Karachi.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

General Objective:

To determine the frequency of maternal infections in females with prelabour rupture of membranes (PROM) at term (≥ 37 weeks) managed with intracervical Foley catheter induction compared to expectant management.

Specific Objectives:

1. To compare the incidence of maternal infections between females induced with intracervical Foley catheter and those managed expectantly.
2. To evaluate the duration between PROM and delivery in both groups.
3. To assess the association between intracervical Foley catheter use and risk of chorioamnionitis.
4. To determine the safety and effectiveness of intracervical Foley catheter as a method of labour induction in PROM cases.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Prelabour rupture of membranes at term is associated with increased risk of maternal and neonatal infections, particularly when there is a delay in delivery. Selecting an appropriate method of labour induction is essential to minimize these risks while ensuring safe maternal and fetal outcomes.

The intracervical Foley catheter is a cost-effective and widely available mechanical method for cervical ripening. Its use is particularly relevant in low-resource settings where access to pharmacological agents may be limited. This study aims to provide evidence regarding the safety and effectiveness of intracervical Foley catheter in PROM, specifically focusing on infection risk. Furthermore, limited local data are available in Pakistan regarding this method. The findings of this study will contribute to evidence-based clinical practice, help optimize management strategies for PROM, and may reduce the incidence of maternal infections, prolonged labour, and unnecessary operative interventions.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Although international studies suggest that intracervical Foley catheter is a safe and effective method for labour induction, there is a lack of local research evaluating its role in PROM cases in Pakistan. Differences in healthcare infrastructure, infection control practices, and patient demographics necessitate region-specific data.

This study is designed to compare intracervical Foley catheter induction with expectant management in terms of maternal infection rates. The results will help guide clinicians in selecting the most appropriate and safe management approach for PROM, while also promoting cost-effective practices in resource-limited healthcare settings.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: The study was a case-control study that was done in the labor room of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi. This research was conducted in a duration of Six months from July 2024- December 2024, following the consent of the research by the

College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP). The study is conducted under the consent of the Institutional Review Board, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi, with approval no: [No.F.2-81/2023-GENL/30/JPMC].

Sample Size: A total of 200 pregnant females were included in the study.

Sampling Technique: Participants were selected using a simple random sampling technique.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Pregnant females who consented to participate
- Singleton pregnancy at term (≥ 37 weeks gestation)
- Females presenting with prelabour rupture of membranes
- Multiparous females
- Cephalic presentation
- Unfavourable cervix at presentation
- No clinical signs of chorioamnionitis at admission

Exclusion Criteria:

- Breech presentation
- Multiple pregnancies
- Placenta previa
- Umbilical cord prolapse
- Previous uterine scar
- Active genital tract infection
- Known medical comorbidities
- Fetal distress
- Clinical chorioamnionitis

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining informed consent, 200 eligible participants with PROM at term were enrolled in the study and divided into two groups:

- **Group A:** Females who underwent induction of labour باستخدام intracervical Foley catheter
- **Group B:** Females managed expectantly

Baseline investigations including total leukocyte count (TLC), C-reactive protein (CRP), urine detailed report, and high vaginal swab were performed at admission.

In Group A, intracervical Foley catheter was inserted under aseptic conditions, and labour was induced. Group B participants were managed expectantly and monitored for spontaneous onset of labour.

All participants were observed for signs and symptoms of infection during labour and postpartum period. Laboratory investigations were repeated when clinically indicated. Participants were followed up for two weeks postpartum to assess maternal infectious outcomes.

Outcome Measures

Primary Outcome:

- Frequency of maternal infections (chorioamnionitis, postpartum infection)

Secondary Outcomes:

- Duration from PROM to delivery
- Mode of delivery
- Laboratory indicators of infection (TLC, CRP, HVS)

Data Analysis Procedure

Data were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for

continuous variables, while frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Chi-square test and independent t-test were applied where appropriate. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality of patient data was maintained throughout the study. The study was conducted in accordance with institutional ethical guidelines.

RESULTS

A total of 200 females with prelabour rupture of membranes (PROM) at term were included in the study and divided into two groups: Group A (intracervical Foley catheter, n = 100) and Group B (expectant management, n = 100).

1. Demographic Characteristics

The mean age of participants in Group A was 27.8 ± 3.1 years, while in Group B it was 27.2 ± 3.4 years. The majority of participants in both groups were between 26–30 years of age. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.29$).

Parity distribution was also comparable, with multiparous خواتين comprising 70% in Group A and 68% in Group B ($p = 0.74$).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Group A (ICF)	Group B (Expectant)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	27.8 ± 3.1	27.2 ± 3.4	0.29
18–25 years (%)	28%	30%	
26–30 years (%)	54%	52%	0.66
>30 years (%)	18%	18%	
Multiparous (%)	70%	68%	0.74

2. Frequency of Maternal Infections

Maternal infections were observed in 11% of females in Group A and 17% in Group B. Although infection rates were lower in the Foley

catheter group, the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.18$).

Chorioamnionitis occurred in 4% of Group A and 8% of Group B, while postpartum infections were observed in 7% and 9%, respectively.

Table 2: Maternal Infection Rates

Infection Type	Group A (ICF)	Group B (Expectant)	p-value
Any Infection (%)	11%	17%	0.18
Chorioamnionitis (%)	4%	8%	0.23
Postpartum Infection (%)	7%	9%	0.60

3. Duration from PROM to Delivery

The mean duration from PROM to delivery was significantly shorter in Group A (13.9 ± 3.4 hours)

compared to Group B (21.8 ± 4.6 hours), and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: PROM to Delivery Interval

Variable	Group A (ICF)	Group B (Expectant)	p-value
Duration (hours)	13.9 ± 3.4	21.8 ± 4.6	<0.001

4. Mode of Delivery

In Group A, 80% of females had vaginal delivery, while 20% underwent cesarean section. In Group

B, 73% had vaginal delivery and 27% had cesarean section. No statistically significant difference was observed ($p = 0.21$).

Table 4: Mode of Delivery

Mode of Delivery	Group A (ICF)	Group B (Expectant)	p-value
Vaginal (%)	80%	73%	0.21
Cesarean (%)	20%	27%	

5. Laboratory Findings

Raised TLC levels were observed in 9% of Group A and 14% of Group B ($p = 0.24$). Elevated CRP levels were found in 10% of Group A and 15% of

Group B ($p = 0.27$). Positive high vaginal swab cultures were noted in 7% of Group A and 12% of Group B ($p = 0.19$). These differences were not statistically significant.

Table 5: Laboratory Findings

Parameter	Group A (ICF)	Group B (Expectant)	p-value
Raised TLC (%)	9%	14%	0.24
Raised CRP (%)	10%	15%	0.27
Positive HVS (%)	7%	12%	0.19

Summary of Findings

Intracervical Foley catheter induction was associated with a shorter PROM-to-delivery interval without a statistically significant increase in maternal infection rates or cesarean section rates when compared to expectant management.

management, remains an area of clinical debate. This study was conducted to compare the frequency of maternal infections in females induced with an intracervical Foley catheter versus those managed expectantly.

DISCUSSION

Prelabour rupture of membranes (PROM) at term is a common obstetric condition associated with increased risk of maternal and neonatal infections. The optimal management strategy, particularly regarding induction of labour versus expectant

In the present study, no statistically significant difference was observed in maternal infection rates between the two groups. Although infection was slightly lower in the intracervical Foley catheter group compared to expectant management, the difference was not significant. These findings are consistent with the study conducted by Hannah et al. (1996), which reported similar infection rates

between induction and expectant management groups, with no increase in cesarean section rates. Similarly, Kruit et al. (2020) demonstrated that the use of a balloon catheter in PROM cases did not significantly increase maternal or neonatal infectious morbidity when appropriate precautions were taken.

The duration from PROM to delivery was significantly shorter in the intracervical Foley catheter group compared to expectant management. This finding supports the concept that active management reduces the latency period, thereby potentially minimizing exposure to ascending infections. Similar results were reported by Shah and Doshi (2012), who concluded that early induction shortens the PROM-to-delivery interval and reduces hospital stay without increasing operative delivery rates. Furthermore, Hayat (2021) also reported that intracervical Foley catheter, especially when combined with other agents, significantly reduces the induction-to-delivery interval.

Regarding mode of delivery, no significant difference was observed between the two groups in this study. The majority of النساء in both groups delivered vaginally, indicating that intracervical Foley catheter does not increase the risk of cesarean section. This finding is supported by Amorosa et al. (2017), who reported no significant difference in delivery outcomes between Foley catheter use and other induction methods.

Laboratory parameters, including TLC, CRP, and high vaginal swab results, were comparable between the two groups, further supporting that intracervical Foley catheter does not increase the risk of infection when used under aseptic conditions. These findings align with previous studies emphasizing the safety of mechanical methods of induction (Greenberg & Khalifeh, 2015).

Overall, the findings of this study suggest that intracervical Foley catheter is a safe and effective method for labour induction in PROM at term. It significantly reduces the duration from PROM to delivery without increasing maternal infection rates or operative deliveries.

However, this study has certain limitations. It was conducted in a single tertiary care center with a

relatively limited sample size, which may affect the generalizability of the results. Additionally, neonatal outcomes were not extensively evaluated, which could be considered in future studies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Intracervical Foley catheter should be considered a safe and effective method for induction of labour in females with PROM at term.
2. Early induction of labour using mechanical methods may be preferred over expectant management to reduce the duration between PROM and delivery.
3. Strict aseptic techniques should be followed during insertion of the Foley catheter to minimize the risk of infection.
4. Routine monitoring of infection markers such as TLC and CRP should be performed in PROM cases.
5. Larger multicenter studies are recommended to further validate these findings and improve generalizability.
6. Future research should also focus on neonatal outcomes associated with different management strategies in PROM.
7. In low-resource settings, intracervical Foley catheter can be promoted as a cost-effective alternative to pharmacological methods of induction.

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